

Conjoint Analysis in the Evaluation of Physical Rapid Prototypes

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Abstract

Small mobile devices with multipurpose functions are becoming an ergonomic problem and a target for growing critics. Because the literature about suitable design and evaluation methods for addressing the design challenge is scarce, we experimented with a novel approach combining Conjoint Analysis (CA) and Rapid Prototypes (RP). CA is used to determine the most preferred combinations in a multivariable choice situation. Rapid prototyping is a recent technology of computer aided prototype production. We organized a test with mobile phone like RP mock-ups to measure the experienced impact of four design attributes. These were phone width and thickness, and the size and location of the keypad. The tests were run with 28 subjects who compared 16 models to a reference model for the convenience of using the keypad. Our experience was that running the tests was fast and fluent. The results proposed that the size and location of keypad were the most influential variables and, thus, the results can be used to focus the design effort. Some challenges related to specifying the evaluation task and attribute levels still remain, and those will be addressed in the discussion.

Keywords: Conjoint Analysis, Product Development, Ergonomics, Mobile Devices

Introduction

Challenge of mobile ergonomics

The development of electronics makes it possible to shrink wireless portable handheld products while introducing increasingly versatile functions like camera, radio and even mobile television. For example, the evolution of GSM mobile phones made by Nokia in 1992-2002 has shown how the average phone size decreased to one fifth of the original (from 340 cm² to 71 cm²) in a decade. At the same time the number of different screens increased almost tenfold (from 406 to 3085). (Lindholm et al. 2003, 12).

In spite of the several benefits that the new features can provide, the shrinking devices are becoming a target for growing public criticism, not least because physical operation is getting demanding and even annoying (e.g. Alexander 2005, Anderson 2005). New applications are also changing the way mobile devices are used. Operating mobile devices used to consist of relatively short sequences: starting a function, reading information, adjusting settings, or writing messages at the longest. Now, playing games or browsing the Internet can be rather lasting, and in the worst case the unpleasantness may turn into repetitive strain injury. A reported problem deals with strain injuries caused by extensive usage of text messaging device Blackberry (Joyce 2005).

The problems with physical operation of mobile terminals have not been fixed by the manufacturers because of the lack of commercial pressure. The vast majority of consumers still seem to accept compromising the ergonomics for other attributes. In fact, there is mixed evidence about consumers' interest and ability to apply ergonomics and usability related criteria in their purchase decisions. According to Yun et al. (2003) for instance the software features and physical ergonomics like button shapes and overall dimensions were considered important. In contrary, the crucial role of other product attributes in decision making (Karjaluoto et al 2005) and the inability of consumers to apply usability related criteria (Keinonen 1998) has been observed. It seems that the only discipline seriously concerned about the physical operation of mobile devices has been design for all (DfA) community and guidelines for the accessibility of mobile phones have been suggested (Roe et al. 1999, Hyppönen 1999), but the proposals have had little impact on the present devices.

Problems with designing physical interfaces do not come as a surprise. The above mentioned trend of increased number of features and decreasing physical interactive surface is just one of the problems. Another one is the fact that the designers of mobile phones and PDAs are short

of guidance. The existing ergonomic standards for keypads and function keys which were created for desktop devices do not stretch to the miniature scales of mobile products. Methods proposed for designing or evaluating the physical interaction are also lacking with few exceptions. These tend to focus on specific interaction challenges like text input rather than the more generic approach to physical ergonomics (e.g. Silfverberg et al 2000, Pavlovych & Stuerzlinger 2004).

One of the challenges in systematical design is that the ergonomics is influenced by several design attributes. The physical operation of a keypad for instance depends on the size of keys, the location of the keypad on the face of the device, the travel characteristics of individual keys to name few. Studying the impact of all of these separately would be very time consuming and easily lead to invalid comparisons as the attributes tend to be connected: bigger keypad requires some keys to be located on the difficult to reach extreme edges of the device, for instance. The smaller the devices are the tighter the connections become. Thus, an answer to focus the effort of systematic design variation and testing could be to apply multivariable approaches such as conjoint analysis.

Ergonomic evaluation

Traditionally ergonomic research has trusted on physiological and subjective approaches. The physiology of handling mobile devices can be measured with electromyography (EMG) or goniometry measurements, but this is rather difficult because of the relatively low powers needed for individual actions. The signals get masked by noise. Another alternative is to trust on subjects' subjective assessment of the experienced strain and needed effort. Different scales for subjective measurements of task load and usability have been developed, but none for assessing the physical ergonomics of mobile devices. Another alternative for developing subjective assessments is to keep the questions simple and experiment with varying the stimuli.

Conjoint analysis

Conjoint analysis (CA) is a method developed and used for marketing research. It is used for determining the most preferred combinations in a multivariable choice situation. Maintaining realistic decision making situation is said to be the strength of CA (Hair et al. 1998). In CA the influence a number of attributes n_A with a given number of attribute levels n_L is studied. Instead of testing the whole combination of $n_A \times n_L$ alternatives, an orthogonal matrix based algorithm is used to reduce the number of combinations needed still maintaining a balanced

selection of attribute levels. The oldest version of method, *Full Profile conjoint analysis*, includes all attributes are in every evaluation. Typically the full profile CA is performed as pair comparison. In *Adaptive Conjoint Analysis (ACA)* the software calculates the offered combinations according the choices subject has all ready made. In full profile CA the practical limit for attributes has been noticed to be six, but ACA makes it possible to handle more attributes and their levels.

Conjoint analysis data can be gathered with various methods. Originally textual written cards were used, but software and Internet based applications have replaced the cards. The process of conducting a CA study (Metsämuuronen 1997) is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. The process of a Conjoint Analysis study.

In marketing research CA is applied to study the influence of product attributes on consumers' product preference. However, the same test design can potentially explain the impact of attributes on consumers' opinions concerning some other properties of a product – ergonomics for instance. In this case textual stimuli should obviously be replaced by something more tangible.

There are several examples of applying CA in product development, but only few where it has been applied especially to ergonomic evaluations (Nygren 1995, Kirvesoja 2001). In these cases the stimulus has been textual. We have found only one study dealing with rear view mirrors where prototypes were used as the stimuli in a ergonomic CA study (Lakshmikantha et al, 2005).

Even with the reduced number of alternatives that the CA algorithm provides, the amount of stimuli needed is a challenge, when the researchers wish to operate with physical 3D models. Creating a dozen or more different 3D models for evaluating ergonomics requires plenty of more labor than the same amount of printed cards. However, fast and already relatively cheap rapid prototyping solutions could speed up the production of 3D stimuli enough to make physical prototypes feasible stimuli to be used in CA.

Rapid prototypes

Rapid prototyping (RP) is a fairly recent technology of computer aided prototype production. With 3D CAD modeling it enables fast realization of several slight variations with equal standards of finishing. Common methods of rapid prototyping like stereo lithography (SLA), selective laser sintering (SLS) 3D printing and fused deposition modeling (FDM) build up physical plastic models layer by layer from CAD models without any molds. Exploiting any of these RP techniques can make conjoint studies with physical prototypes a relatively fast and cost efficient method. In studying hand ergonomics the physical models are needed if ever. More about rapid prototyping see e.g. Pham & Dimov (2001).

Research objectives

The objective of our study is to develop and pilot a method for evaluating the physical ergonomics of a handheld interactive device. We have been aiming at an approach having the following characteristics:

- subjective evaluation that depends on target group members' personal assessments of the ergonomic quality of a solution
- multivariable measurement where the relative impact of several possibly influencing design variables can be studied with one single test setting
- fast and cost efficient method enabling it to be applied in practical product development context.

We have assumed that above mentioned aims could be achieved with combining Conjoint Analysis (CA) as a multivariable test process with three dimensional stimuli created by Rapid Prototyping (RP) techniques. We claim that the experiment has relevance on HCI forum, because the physical ergonomics of mobile devices has been a neglected topic and because

the proposed kind of combination of research approaches has not been applied in the research of mobile ergonomics before.

To summarize our objectives into a hypothesis we assume that by applying Conjoint Analysis and Rapid Prototyping, it is possible to get design relevant information about product attributes influencing the ergonomics of mobile hand-held devices.

Method

To validate the hypothesis, we conducted a CA study with a commercial conjoint analysis software (QPR Market Maker). The software was used both in determining the set of tested products and in later data analysis. Mobile phone -like mock-ups were selected as the stimuli with which the influences of different attributes were studied. The CA software calculated 16 samples to be tested against a reference model from the total of 192 possible combinations. Thirty subjects were asked to evaluate the convenience of using the keypads of the models and to divide ten points between the models according to their decision.

Attributes, attribute levels and samples

In CA using relevant attributes is vital for getting reliable information (Hair et al. 1998). For making the experiment test results easier to interpret we decided to choose attributes that were thought to be relatively independent of each others. The attributes needed also to be relevant for design and relatively easy to build into the sample models. In actual product development, a more appropriate way to define the attributes would probably be interviewing and observing the target segment and choosing the features to test based on the results. Because of limited time and our focus being on evaluating the method rather than providing information for real design cases, a short cut process was regarded adequate. The chosen attributes were phone width, phone thickness, keypad size and keypad location (distance from the bottom of the phone).

Attribute levels were chosen so that they were within the range of existing phone models of Nokia, Sony-Ericsson and Motorola. Four levels were selected to be able acquire enough information for seeing trends between attribute levels and to keep the number of models reasonable to produce and evaluate. Other attributes like phone length, fillets and display sizes were standardized. See table 1 for the attributes and attribute levels.

Table 1. Attributes and attribute levels.

Attributes	Attribute levels			
Phone width	50 mm	46 mm	42 mm	38 mm
Phone thickness	16 mm	18 mm	20 mm	22 mm
Keypad size (height)	34 mm	40 mm	46 mm	
Keypad location (distance of lowest keys from the bottom)	5 mm	10 mm	15 mm	20 mm

Full factorial design where all the levels of all the attributes were produced would have results $4 \times 4 \times 4 \times 3 = 192$ combinations. CA software optimized the combinations for prototypes with orthogonal series estimation. It produced orthogonal co-ordinates dimensions $(4-1) + (4-1) + (4-1) + (3-1) = 11$ where number 11 is the sum of attributes main effects. This amount of different profiles is the minimum needed to find out the main effects of the attributes. The software suggested 16 combinations. In addition, one duplicate model and a hold out model were added. Hold out model is used for checking the consistency of the answers. Reference model which was used in comparison had two copies to make the test situation smooth. These made altogether 20 sample models. See table 2 for each model's attribute levels.

Table 2. Models and their attribute levels. Hold out, duplicate (of model no 1) and reference models marked with grey background.

	Model no.																		H	Dup	Ref
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18			
phone width (mm)	38	50	38	42	46	46	50	42	38	46	42	38	50	46	50	42	38	38	42		
-"- thickness (mm)	18	20	20	16	18	20	22	18	16	22	22	22	18	16	16	20	16	18	18		
keypad size (mm)	40	40	40	40	46	34	34	34	34	40	40	46	40	40	46	46	34	40	40		
-"- location (mm)	10	20	15	15	15	10	15	20	5	5	10	20	5	20	10	5	20	10	10		

The modeling was done by AliasWavefront[®] modeling software. To make it easier to vary the dimensions and to create the 3D models the design was extremely simplified (figure 2). This was also done not to distract the subjects' attention from the test attributes to attention catching appearance. Rapid prototypes were made with FDM method.

Figure 2. CAD images of samples number 12 and 15.

Subjects

Test was conducted with 30 subjects of whom 28 (14 female, 14 male) produced results that could be used in the analysis. The age of 17 subjects was 20-39 years, 7 between 40-60 years and four was over 60. Test subjects were mainly students and staff of a university design department.

The hand sizes of the subjects were measured and categorized based on anthropometrics of world adult population by Jürgens et al (1990) who divide world population into large and small. The P95 of the small population equals to P5 of the large population. Table 3 presents the hand sizes of our sample and a comparison to Jürgens et al global distributions. Possible deficiencies of hand were asked and all but one said that they have healthy hands with no injuries or pains. All subjects had short fingernails. To find out possible correlation between own mobile phone and ergonomic preferences the dimensions of subjects' mobile phones were also measured.

Table 3. Hand sizes of subjects compared to Jürgens at all (1990) global distribution.

Jürgens at all (1990) global distribution					
	small type			large type	
	P5	P50	P95/P5	P50	P95
length	140 mm	155 mm	170 mm	185 mm	200 mm
width	65 mm	75 mm	90 mm	100 mm	110 mm
Sample subjects' hands (n)					
length	under 155 mm (1)	155 - 170 mm (3)	170 - 185 mm (12)	over 185 mm (12)	
width	under 75 mm (1)	75 - 90 mm (16)	90 - 100 mm (10)	over 100 mm (1)	

Test Procedure

The test started by introducing the procedure and the rapid prototypes. The subjects were led to the evaluation process by advising them to test, for example, the reach of the thumb on the corners of the keypad, and to feel the general shape of the phone models. They were asked to compare the hand ergonomics of two rapid prototype models at a time and then to divide ten points to the models according their decision. In the pilot test, the evaluation was made with 100 points, but this seemed to be difficult for the subjects and a more robust scale was applied instead.

The two models to be compared at a time were handed together to the subject; the other one being one or the other of the reference model copies through the whole test. Most subjects did not recognize that reference model did not change. The subject tested the models in hand, declared the points and gave the models back to the moderator. The test started with two warm up evaluations after which the comparisons were recorded. After the comparisons the subjects' background information was gathered. For an overview of the test setup see figure 3.

Figure 3. CA test setup. In Conjoint Analysis the subjects make a series of pair comparisons, in which they divide ten points between each pair.

Results

The tests were conducted without major problems. The first few judgments seemed to take longer and as the subject got used to the test the decisions became faster. Some subjects were using mainly 0-10 evaluation style giving all the points to either of the evaluated models, but most were more moderate in their choices. The time for all the evaluations was about 20 minutes in average. Some subjects were either showing marks of tiredness or explicitly asked if there were still many to go when the test approach the end which indicates that the test was probably as long as it can be.

A recurring remark of several subjects during the test was that “Although the other one looked better initially, I have to give better points to this one.” Obviously, the appearance of the models created expectations about the ergonomics which then tactile response did not confirm. The subjects were slightly surprised with what they felt and they had to deal with conflicting information.

The results are calculated based on 28 subjects the hold-out correlation being 0,609 which is lower than typically achieved with traditional verbal stimuli. The average scores given to each model are presented in table 4.

Table 3. Average comparison score of each model from all subjects. Score of 5 means equally good with the reference model.

	Model no.																H	Dup
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16		
average score	4,5	4,5	4,7	6,0	6,2	3,1	3,1	4,6	2,6	3,3	4,5	5,1	3,5	6,1	4,6	4,6	4,1	4,7

The results show that keypad size and keypad location are the attributes having the biggest impact on subjective evaluation of physical handling of the mock-ups, keypad size explaining 33% and keypad location 31% of the variation. Thickness and width explain 17 % and 19 % correspondingly (see figure 4). The most favorably assessed size of keypad is the largest one and the still growing graph suggests that the best valued size would be even larger (see figure 5). Keypad location should be about 20 mm or more above the bottom of the phone to achieve the best comfort (see figure 6).

Figure 4. The capability of the attributes to explain the subjects' comparison results. The most important attributes are keypad size (33%) and location (31%).

Figure 5. The influence of keypad size (mm) on comparisons.

Figure 6. The influence of keypad location (mm) on comparisons.

When the sample was divided into small and large handed segments, the results remained surprisingly similar, i.e. hand size did not seem to have significant impact on the assessment. Similar comparisons were made between older and younger segments as well as between the segments of large phone and small phone owners. The results do not reveal any significant differences between the segments excluding the small segment of subjects (n=4) whose own phone was wider than 50 mm. They did not give any weight at all on the width of a phone.

The results showed that the keypad size and the location of the keypad, explaining 64 % of the preference, were considered more important than the other attributes. The analysis also suggested optimum values for some of the attributes. Especially attention to the importance of

the free space under the keys is an interesting finding. It was considered as important as the size of the keypad. The test procedure required approximately 30 minutes per subject, thus, it was possible to carry out the whole test series by one person in just three days.

As a conclusion, the conjoint analysis converted into an ergonomic research tool with rapid prototypes as stimulus, seems to be applicable to subjective evaluation of the ergonomic dimensions of small mobile devices and it seems to produce relevant data fairly effortlessly for the needs of product development. The results like the ones we achieved, we believe, are relevant for guiding the design focus towards the most critical aspects from the point of view of ergonomics.

Discussion

We concluded that we consider Conjoint Analysis with Rapid Prototyping as a possible method for studying ergonomics of mobile devices. However, we are not completely satisfied with the first experiment we completed. An obvious indication of our problems is the low hold-out correlation.

There are two main reasons which we expect to influence on the subjects' inconsistent answers. First, there seemed to be some confusion among the subjects about what they should evaluate. We asked them to compare the models on the basis of the convenience of using keypads, the primary source of information being tactile feel of the mock-ups. However, the subjects seemed to pay also attention to the overall appearance and appeal of the models and we have no data to estimate the impact of the latter to the former. The next version of the test should pay special attention this problem by explicitly measuring the overall preference. Another possible reason for the inconsistent answers was the lack of cognitive control. It was obvious that the attributes and attribute levels were difficult or impossible to memorize. The subjects were not able to compare the new blocks they were given to their previous answers, but only to the reference model. Thus, each comparison was probably like a new decision making situation and cumulative learning did not take place during the test. Subjects' ability to learn the attributes and attribute levels during the test depends on the range and character of the attributes and, therefore, further experiments should be done to learn to understand the phenomenon better.

In our experiment we did not aim at solving real product development challenges because of the experimental nature of the study and the lack of dialogue with industry. A necessary next

step for developing the approach will be to ensure the practical relevance of the studied attributes with mobile device design teams.

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